

Spatial Distribution, Phytoavailability and Soil-Cassava Transfer of Heavy Metals in Mechanic Village Impacted Soils of Egbu, Imo State, Nigeria

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Abstract: This study evaluated heavy metal distribution, soil–cassava transfer, and contamination risk in mechanic village impacted soils of Egbu, Imo State, Nigeria. Geo-referenced surface soils (0–20 cm) and cassava (*Manihot esculenta*) samples were collected using a grid-based design, alongside control sites. Soil physicochemical properties and concentrations of Cd, Cr, As, Ni, and Fe were determined via standard analytical procedures and Atomic Absorption Spectrophotometry. Pollution indices (CF, Cd, PLI), bioaccumulation factor (BAF), and biotranslocation factor (BTF) were applied to assess contamination status and transfer dynamics. Soils were predominantly sandy with slightly acidic pH, conditions favoring metal mobility. Cd exceeded permissible limits across all sites, while Cr, As, Ni, and Fe remained below thresholds in soils. However, cassava tissues exhibited elevated Cd, Cr, and As concentrations above FAO/WHO limits, with peels > tubers. CF and PLI indicated severe Cd contamination and moderate overall soil pollution, while BAF (>1) confirmed active uptake and accumulation, particularly for Cd and Cr. Results demonstrate efficient soil–plant transfer of toxic metals and highlight cassava as a critical exposure pathway in mechanic village environments.

Keywords: Heavy metals, Cadmium contamination, Mechanic village pollution, Soil–plant transfer, Cassava (*Manihot esculenta*)

1.0. Introduction

Heavy metal contamination of soils has become a growing environmental concern, particularly in developing countries where rapid urbanization and informal industrial activities are common. Metals such as cadmium (Cd), chromium (Cr), arsenic (As), and nickel (Ni) are of particular concern because they are persistent, non-biodegradable, and can accumulate in soils to levels that threaten ecosystem health and food safety (Onakpa et al., 2018). In Nigeria, the expansion of unregulated activities has significantly increased the risk of soil contamination, especially in urban and peri-urban areas. Mechanic villages are among the major but often overlooked sources of this contamination. Routine activities such as engine repairs, disposal of spent oil, battery leakage, and metal scrap handling introduce heavy metals into surrounding soils. Over time, these pollutants build up and may alter soil quality, posing risks to both the environment and agricultural productivity. Although studies in southeastern Nigeria have reported elevated heavy metal levels in soils affected by human activities (Okereke et al., 2020), there is still limited

site-specific information for many locations, including Egbu in Imo State.

Cassava (*Manihot esculenta* Crantz), a widely consumed staple in Nigeria, is commonly cultivated in areas close to such pollution sources. Due to its ability to absorb and accumulate heavy metals from the soil, cassava can serve as a pathway for transferring contaminants into the human food chain. Previous studies have shown that cassava grown on contaminated soils may contain elevated levels of heavy metals, raising concerns about long-term health risks (Emurotu & Onianwa, 2017). However, the extent to which these metals are transferred from soil to cassava in mechanic village-impacted environments remains insufficiently understood. In Egbu, where agricultural activities coexist with automobile repair operations, there is a clear need for localized data to better understand the distribution of heavy metals in soils and their uptake by food crops. Such information is essential for assessing environmental quality, ensuring food safety, and supporting informed land-use decisions. Therefore, this study aims to evaluate the distribution of heavy metals in

mechanic village–impacted soils of Egbu, Imo State, and their transfer into cassava.

2.0 Materials and Methods

2.1 Study Area

The study was conducted in Egbu, located in Owerri North Local Government Area of Imo State, southeastern Nigeria. The area hosts an active mechanic village characterized by automobile repair activities such as engine servicing, welding,

battery handling, and disposal of spent lubricants. These activities are known to introduce heavy metals into surrounding environments through uncontrolled waste disposal and oil spillage (Onianwa & Fakayode, 2000; Okeke et al., 2020). The climate is humid tropical with distinct wet and dry seasons, and the soils are generally derived from coastal plain sands, supporting arable crop production, particularly cassava (FAO, 2019).

Figure 1: Map of Imo State Showing the Study Location

2.2 Sampling Design and Soil Collection

A rigid grid sampling technique was used to ensure representativeness across farmland plots near the mechanic villages. The soil samples were collected in the four cardinal

points, north, south, east and west. This was achieved with the help of compass while at the center of the mechanic village. A grid of 4m x 4m was done at each direction and soil samples were collected

at random within the grid from the topsoil layer (0 – 20 cm), where heavy metals are most concentrated (Alloway, 2013). At each cardinal point, five subsamples were taken given a total of 20 soil samples from farmlands around Egbu Mechanic Villages. Five farmlands were selected 500m away from the mechanic village which served as the control. Cassava tubers were collected from the same farmland plots where soil samples were taken. At each of the cardinal point, five mature tubers were collected closely to where the soil samples were taken. Cassava samples were washed, peeled, oven-dried separately at 40°C and ground. All soil and cassava samples were placed in labeled polythene bags, transported to the laboratory; air-dried soils were also stored under appropriate conditions until analysis (FAO, 2006). A Germin eTtrex SE handheld GPS device was used to mark and record the geographic coordinates (latitude and longitude) of each sampled points. A total of 25 geo-referenced soil sampling points was used for this study. The study area was mapped using ArcGIS software.

2.3 Laboratory Analysis

All soil analyses were conducted following standard methods described by the Soil Science Society of America (SSSA) and International Institute of Tropical Agriculture (IITA). Soil pH was determined in a 1:2.5 soil-to-water suspension using a calibrated digital pH meter (Thomas, 1996). Organic carbon was determined using the Walkley and Black wet oxidation method (Nelson & Sommers, 1982). Soil texture was determined by the hydrometer method (Gee & Or, 2002). Soil and cassava samples was digested using aqua regia (HNO₃: HCl, 1:3) (USEPA, 1996). The samples were analyzed for heavy metal of Pb, Cd, Cr, Ni, and Fe using Atomic Absorption Spectrophotometry (AAS) (Lindsay & Norvell, 1978). The choice of these metals was because they are associated with mechanic workshop pollution. To ensure quality control, analytical blanks and certified reference materials was included in each batch. All measurements were done in triplicates.

2.4 Assessment of Pollution Potential Contamination Factor (CF)

To determine the extent of metal contamination in the farmlands soils around

the Egbu mechanic village contamination factor was used. According to Tomlinson et al. (1980) contamination factor is expressed as:

$$CF = C_{\text{metal}} / C_{\text{background}}$$

Where:

C_{metal} is the present metal concentration in the sampled soil.

$C_{\text{background}}$ is the background metal concentration of soil.

The upper continental crust proposed by Rudnick & Gao (2003) was used as the background metal concentration. The CF is interpreted as follows: $CF < 1$: implies low contamination; $1 \leq CF < 3$: implies moderate contamination; $3 \leq CF \leq 6$: implies considerable contamination and $CF \geq 6$: implies very high contamination.

2.5 Degree of Contamination (C_d)

To further determine the extent farmland soils around the mechanic village has been polluted, the degree of contamination proposed by Hakanson (1980) was employed and is given as:

$$C_d = \sum CF$$

The degree of contamination of an element is computed by summing up the contamination factors of a particular element in the samples. The interpretation

of C_d is given as: $C_d < 6$ shows low C_d ; $6 < C_d < 12$ means moderate C_d ; $12 < C_d < 24$ is considerable C_d while $C_d > 24$ is high C_d and shows strong anthropogenic pollution.

2.6 Pollution Load Index (PLI)

The bio-concentration factor was used to assess the level of heavy metal concentrations in soil and plant samples. As stated by Tomlinson et al. (1980), the pollution load index is defined as follows:

$$PLI = \sqrt[n]{CF_1 \times CF_2 \dots \times CF_n}$$

Where:

The variable n denotes the number of heavy metals, whereas CF refers to the contamination factor. When the PLI value < 1 , the area is considered unpolluted; a PLI of 1 implies that the heavy metal load is nearly equal to the background level, and a $PLI > 1$ indicates pollution (Cabrera et al., 1999).

2.7 Bioaccumulation and Transfer Factor Analysis

The bio-accumulation factor was utilized to assess the level of heavy metal concentrations in the peels and tubers of *M. esculenta* samples. According to Yoon et al. (2006), the bio-concentration factor is defined as follows:

BAF (peels) = P_{mc}/S_{mc}

BAF (tubers) = T_{mc}/S_{mc}

Where:

The concentrations of heavy metals in the peels and tubers are represented by P_{mc} and T_{mc} , respectively, whereas S_{mc} refers to the metal concentration in the soil.

BAF > 1, it signifies hyperaccumulation.

2.8 Data Analysis

The data was subjected to descriptive statistics so as to determine the Mean and standard deviation of metal concentrations in soils and cassava. Analysis of variance was used to test differences across the different four cardinal points sampled together with the control site. Correlation Analysis was used to determine the relationship between soil properties and metal accumulation in cassava. The results were presented in tables and graph. Data was analyzed using SPSS.

3.0 Results and Discussion

3.1 The Physical Properties of the soils around Egbu mechanic village

The particle size distribution of soils around Egbu Mechanic Village reveals a dominance of sandy fractions, with clay content ranging from 8.40–10.40% and showing no

significant variation ($p < 0.05$) across all sampling directions (Table 1). The generally low clay content suggests limited surface area for adsorption and reduced cation exchange capacity, which can impair nutrient retention and increase contaminant mobility in soils (Nie & Huang, 2024). Silt content exhibited slight variability, with higher values in the control and northern directions compared to the west, likely reflecting localized disturbance from anthropogenic activities. Fine sand and coarse sand fractions dominated across all locations, with coarse sand particularly high in the east and control sites. This sandy dominance indicates high permeability and low water-holding capacity, characteristics widely associated with reduced soil fertility and enhanced leaching potential (Musei et al., 2024; Alghamdi et al., 2023).

Texturally, the soils were mainly classified as sandy loam and loamy sand. The control site maintained sandy loam, whereas impacted areas showed a mixture of both classes, with loamy sand indicating poorer structural stability and nutrient retention. Coarse-textured soils such as these are known to facilitate the vertical migration of contaminants, particularly heavy metals,

thereby increasing the risk of groundwater pollution (Ramos-Romero et al., 2026).

Overall, the soils in the study area are coarse-textured and weakly structured, making them highly susceptible to nutrient depletion and contaminant transport. The

observed spatial variability in sand fractions further highlights the influence of mechanical and anthropogenic activities typical of mechanic villages, which may accelerate soil degradation and environmental risk.

Table 1: Physical Properties of the soils around Egbu mechanic village

Directions	Sampling points	Clay	Silt	FS %	CS	Textural Class
Control	1	12.00	13.00	36.00	39.00	Sandy Loam
	2	12.00	9.00	32.00	47.00	Sandy Loam
	3	8.00	17.00	30.00	51.00	Sandy Loam
	4	12.00	9.00	32.00	47.00	Sandy Loam
	5	8.00	17.00	30.00	51.00	Sandy Loam
Mean ±STD		10.40±2.19a	13.00±4.00a	32.00±2.45a	47.00±4.90ab	
East	1	10.00	7.00	22.00	61.00	Sandy Loam
	2	8.00	7.00	26.00	59.00	Loamy Sand
	3	8.00	9.00	30.00	53.00	Loamy Sand
	4	8.00	7.00	53.00	32.00	Loamy Sand
	5	8.00	11.00	26.00	55.00	Sandy Loam
Mean ±STD		8.40±0.89a	8.20±1.79bc	31.40±12.40a	52.00±11.62a	
North	1	10.00	15.00	56.00	19.00	Sandy Loam
	2	10.00	15.00	66.00	9.00	Sandy Loam
	3	8.00	13.00	27.00	52.00	Loamy Sand
	4	8.00	7.00	62.00	23.00	Loamy Sand
	5	10.00	9.00	33.00	48.00	Sandy Loam
Mean ±STD		9.20±1.10a	11.80±3.63ab	48.80±17.66a	30.20±18.83b	
West	1	8.00	5.00	32.00	55.00	Loamy Sand
	2	12.00	7.00	64.00	17.00	Sandy Loam
	3	10.00	9.00	36.00	45.00	Sandy Loam
	4	12.00	5.00	59.00	24.00	Sandy Loam
	5	10.00	9.00	39.00	42.00	Sandy Loam
Mean ±STD		10.40±1.67a	7.00±2.00c	46.00±14.47a	36.60±15.66ab	
South	1	8.00	7.00	39.00	46.00	Loamy Sand
	2	8.00	7.00	61.00	24.00	Loamy Sand
	3	8.00	9.00	27.00	56.00	Loamy Sand
	4	10.00	11.00	36.00	43.00	Sandy Loam
	5	8.00	7.00	48.00	37.00	Loamy Sand
Mean ±STD		8.40±0.89a	8.20±1.79bc	42.20±12.91a	41.20±11.82ab	

3.2 The chemical Properties of the soils around Egbu mechanic village

Table 2 represents the chemical properties of the soils proximal to the mechanic village. The soils in the study area were generally slightly acidic to near neutral, with

pH (H₂O) ranging from 5.96 to 6.76. The control and eastern locations recorded higher pH values, while the southern, western, and northern directions were significantly more acidic (p < 0.05). A similar

trend was observed for pH (KCl), with lower values indicating higher exchangeable acidity, particularly in the southern direction. The consistent difference between pH (H₂O) and pH (KCl) suggests the presence of exchangeable acidic cations, which can influence nutrient availability and increase heavy metal solubility (Neina, 2019). Organic matter (OM) content ranged from 2.04% to 3.03%, with the control and northern directions showing relatively higher values, while the western direction recorded significantly lower OM ($p < 0.05$).

The reduced OM in impacted areas may be

attributed to continuous mechanical disturbances and contamination associated with mechanic activities, which can accelerate organic matter degradation (Wiesmeier et al., 2019). Generally, the moderate acidity and variable organic matter content indicate that while the soils may support plant growth, increased acidity and reduced OM in some locations could enhance heavy metal mobility and reduce soil fertility. This highlights the influence of anthropogenic activities on soil chemical quality in the study area (Zhang et al., 2023).

Table 2: Chemical Properties of the soils around Egbu mechanic village

Directions	Sampling points	pH (H ₂ O)	pH (KCl)	Organic Matter %
Control	1	6.60	5.60	4.20
	2	6.60	5.80	3.15
	3	7.00	6.00	2.32
	4	6.60	5.80	3.15
	5	7.00	6.00	2.32
Mean ±STD		6.760±0.22a	5.84±0.17a	3.03±0.77a
East	1	6.90	5.90	2.32
	2	6.80	6.00	3.00
	3	6.70	5.90	2.85
	4	6.60	6.00	2.40
	5	6.80	6.00	2.25
Mean ±STD		6.760±0.11a	5.96±0.05a	2.56±0.34ab
North	1	6.40	5.30	3.67
	2	6.20	4.80	2.55
	3	6.50	5.30	3.76
	4	6.50	5.40	2.55
	5	5.90	4.90	2.47
Mean ±STD		6.30±0.26b	5.14±0.27b	3.00±0.65a
West	1	6.80	5.70	1.73
	2	6.40	5.50	2.17
	3	5.90	4.80	2.32
	4	5.90	4.70	2.02
	5	5.80	4.70	1.95
Mean ±STD		6.16±0.43b	5.08±0.48b	2.04±0.23b
South	1	5.80	4.50	2.32
	2	5.70	4.50	3.00
	3	6.00	4.70	3.15
	4	6.10	4.60	1.65
	5	6.20	5.00	3.45
Mean ±STD		5.96±0.21b	4.66±0.21c	2.71±0.72ab

3.3 Heavy metal content on the soils around Egbu mechanic village

The concentrations of Cd, Cr, As, Ni, and Fe in the soils (Table 3) show clear spatial variation, reflecting both natural background levels and the influence of mechanic activities in the area. Cadmium (Cd) levels ranged from 3.34 to 6.83 mg/kg across the study sites, with all locations including the control (5.12 mg/kg) exceeding the FAO/WHO permissible limit of 3.00 mg/kg. The highest values recorded in the eastern direction suggest localized contamination, likely from sources such as used batteries, lubricants, and metal scraps. This widespread elevation of Cd is environmentally significant due to its high toxicity and mobility, especially in slightly acidic soils (Zhang et al., 2023).

In contrast, chromium (Cr), arsenic (As), and nickel (Ni) concentrations were relatively low and remained within their respective permissible limits. Chromium ranged from 1.09 to 6.03 mg/kg, arsenic from 1.12 to

1.50 mg/kg, and nickel from 1.95 to 3.50 mg/kg. Although these values do not indicate immediate contamination, their presence suggests minor contributions from anthropogenic activities and highlights the need for continued monitoring, as these metals can accumulate over time (Nie & Huang, 2024). Iron (Fe) concentrations were also low (2.69–3.58 mg/kg) compared to the permissible limit and showed little variation across the study area, indicating a predominantly natural (geogenic) origin.

Finally, the results show that cadmium is the major contaminant of concern in the study area, while other metals remain within safe limits. The combination of slightly acidic soil conditions and sandy texture may further enhance the mobility of Cd, increasing the risk of its transfer into plants and groundwater systems. These findings highlight the impact of mechanic village activities on soil quality and the need for proper management to reduce environmental risks (Neina, 2019).

Table 3: Heavy metal content on the soils around Egbu mechanic village

Directions	Sampling points	Cd	Cr	As	Ni	Fe
		mg/kg				
Control	1	4.66	9.62	1.29	4.34	3.36
	2	5.43	3.64	1.11	3.87	3.92
	3	5.43	3.64	1.32	2.47	2.24
	4	4.66	9.62	1.29	4.34	3.36
	5	5.43	3.64	1.32	2.47	2.24
Mean ±STD		5.12±0.42ab	6.03±3.27a	1.26±0.09b	3.50±0.96a	3.02±0.75a
East	1	6.98	5.20	1.26	3.40	3.36
	2	5.82	3.12	1.02	3.70	2.80
	3	6.21	5.20	1.17	1.64	1.68
	4	9.70	1.04	1.11	1.94	2.24
	5	5.43	4.42	1.049	4.343	3.36
Mean ±STD		6.83±1.70a	3.80±1.76ab	1.12±0.10c	3.00±1.16ab	2.69±0.73a
North	1	5.04	4.94	1.26	2.41	2.80
	2	6.21	0.52	1.29	0.88	3.36
	3	2.72	2.34	1.53	1.76	4.48
	4	10.09	2.08	1.50	2.88	2.80
	5	3.49	1.56	1.44	1.82	4.48
Mean ±STD		5.51±2.89ab	2.29±1.64bc	1.40±0.12a	1.95±0.75b	3.58±0.85a
West	1	1.94	1.30	1.53	2.58	4.48
	2	8.15	0.52	1.47	3.23	2.80
	3	2.33	0.52	1.53	1.82	2.80
	4	1.94	0.52	1.35	2.99	2.80
	5	2.33	2.60	1.65	3.58	4.48
Mean ±STD		3.34±2.70b	1.09±0.91c	1.50±0.11a	2.84±0.68ab	3.47±0.92a
South	1	3.88	3.12	1.20	2.35	3.92
	2	3.88	3.12	1.32	1.82	2.24
	3	2.33	3.12	1.26	2.88	2.80
	4	4.27	2.86	1.20	2.52	3.36
	5	10.09	3.90	1.05	2.00	3.92
Mean ±STD		4.89±3.00ab	3.22±0.39bc	1.20±0.10bc	2.31±0.42ab	3.25±0.73a
SPL(FAO/WHO)		3.00	100.00	20.00	50.00	5000.00

SPL = Soil Permissible Limit for Heavy Metals

3.4 The inter-relationship between soil properties and selected heavy metals in the soil

The inter-relationship between soil properties and heavy metals (Table 4) provides insight into the controls of metal distribution, phytoavailability, and soil–cassava transfer dynamics in the study area. The strong inverse correlation between fine sand (FS) and coarse sand (CS) ($r = -0.97$, $p < 0.01$) confirms textural heterogeneity and

highlights the influence of particle size on metal retention, with finer fractions enhancing adsorption capacity due to greater surface area (Alloway, 2013). The strong positive relationship between pH (H₂O) and pH (KCl) ($r = 0.95$, $p < 0.01$) indicates consistency in soil acidity, while their moderate positive associations with Cd and Ni suggest reduced mobility and increased retention under near-neutral

conditions, consistent with established pH-controlled metal solubility dynamics (Adriano, 2001; Mkhonza et al., 2026).

Organic matter (OM) showed a significant positive correlation with Cr ($r = 0.57, p < 0.05$), indicating stabilization through complexation, whereas weak relationships with other metals reflect element-specific interactions (Zhang et al., 2020). The significant association between Ni and Cr ($r = 0.56, p < 0.05$) suggests a common anthropogenic source, likely linked to mechanic village activities (Iwegbue et al., 2013). In contrast, Cd exhibited relatively higher mobility, as indicated by its association with sandy fractions and weak binding to clay, implying greater phytoavailability and potential uptake by cassava. Arsenic showed negative correlations with pH and OM, suggesting increased mobility under acidic conditions,

while Fe displayed weak associations overall, indicating control by inherent soil mineralogy, though its relationship with arsenic suggests adsorption onto iron oxides (Smedley & Kinniburgh, 2002).

Overall, soil pH, organic matter, and texture are key determinants of heavy metal behavior, although their influence varies among elements. The results indicate combined geogenic and anthropogenic controls, with evidence of co-contamination and differential mobility. Notably, relatively mobile metals such as Cd and Ni pose greater risks of soil–plant transfer and food chain contamination. These findings underscore the need for integrated assessment approaches, including transfer factors and health risk indices, to better evaluate contamination risks in agroecosystems (Tiabou et al., 2024; Mkhonza et al., 2026).

Table 4: The inter-relationship between soil properties and selected heavy metals in the soil

	<i>Clay</i>	<i>Silt</i>	<i>FS</i>	<i>CS</i>	<i>pH H₂O</i>	<i>pH KCl</i>	<i>OM</i>	<i>Cd</i>	<i>Cr</i>	<i>Ars</i>	<i>Ni</i>	<i>Fe</i>
Clay	1											
Silt	-0.04	1										
FS	0.20	-0.14	1									
CS	-0.32	-0.03	-0.97**	1								
pH H ₂ O	-0.15	0.32	-0.41	0.39	1							
pH KCl	-0.08	0.19	-0.39	0.38	0.95**	1						
OM	0.08	0.26	-0.05	-0.04	0.09	0.11	1					
Cd	-0.15	-0.06	0.35	-0.30	0.38	0.41	0.11	1				
Cr	0.22	0.25	-0.39	0.30	0.36	0.36	0.57*	0.05	1			
Ars	0.16	0.00	0.16	-0.17	-0.28	-0.31	-0.24	-0.42	-0.32	1		
Ni	0.43	-0.14	-0.34	0.30	0.32	0.39	0.09	-0.04	0.56*	-0.15	1	
Fe	0.17	-0.16	-0.22	0.19	-0.23	-0.27	-0.01	-0.32	-0.05	0.30	0.14	1

3.5 Heavy metal content on the peels of cassava harvested from the soil around Egbu mechanic village

The concentrations of heavy metals in cassava peels indicate substantial accumulation of Cd, Cr, and As across all sampling locations (Table 5). Cadmium ranged from 14.55 to 24.05 mg/kg, far exceeding the FAO/WHO permissible limit of 0.20 mg/kg, with similarly high values observed even at the control site. This suggests strong soil–plant transfer and highlights Cd as the primary contaminant of concern, likely enhanced by acidic soil conditions and high mobility (Zhang et al., 2023). Chromium concentrations (6.11–17.55 mg/kg) also exceeded the permissible limit of 1.30 mg/kg in all directions, with the highest values recorded in the south. Despite relatively low soil Cr levels, its elevated presence in cassava peels indicates effective uptake and accumulation by the plant (Alloway, 2013).

Arsenic levels (1.99–3.48 mg/kg) were consistently above the permissible limit of 0.10 mg/kg, particularly in the northern and western directions. This suggests bioaccumulation over time and raises concerns due to its toxicity even at low concentrations (Ramos-Romero et al., 2026). In contrast, nickel (8.30–12.91 mg/kg) and iron (20.16–44.52 mg/kg) remained within their respective permissible limits, indicating lower immediate risk. However, their presence still reflects ongoing uptake from contaminated soils (Nie & Huang, 2024). The results demonstrate significant contamination of cassava peels by toxic metals, particularly Cd, Cr, and As, highlighting the influence of mechanic village activities and the potential risk to human health through food consumption. The findings underscore the need for continuous monitoring and management of agricultural practices in the area (Neina, 2019).

Table 5: Heavy metal content on the peel of cassava harvested from the soils around Egbu mechanic village

Directions	Sampling points	Cd	Cr	As	Ni	Fe
		mg/kg				
Control	1	21.33	13.00	2.06	13.79	16.80
	2	22.30	13.00	1.87	14.53	21.00
	3	24.24	9.75	2.06	10.86	25.20
	4	22.30	13.00	1.87	14.53	21.00
	5	24.24	9.75	2.06	10.86	25.20
Mean ±STD		22.88±1.30a	11.70±1.78b	1.99±0.10c	12.91±1.90a	21.84±3.51b
East	1	13.58	6.50	3.75	12.62	50.40
	2	14.55	7.80	2.62	16.58	44.80
	3	12.61	3.25	2.44	5.14	37.80
	4	13.58	6.50	3.75	12.62	50.40
	5	43.64	6.50	2.81	9.83	39.20
Mean ±STD		19.59±13.46a	6.11±1.69c	3.07±0.63ab	11.36±4.23ab	44.52±5.97a
North	1	15.52	12.35	2.81	10.86	21.00
	2	16.49	7.80	3.00	13.35	19.60
	3	23.27	9.75	3.37	7.04	15.40
	4	45.58	9.75	3.93	11.00	26.60
	5	19.39	10.40	4.31	9.83	18.20
Mean ±STD		24.05±12.41a	10.01±1.63b	3.48±0.63a	10.42±2.28ab	20.16±4.15b
West	1	15.52	14.95	2.44	8.51	14.00
	2	14.55	9.75	3.56	8.07	22.40
	3	14.55	7.80	2.81	6.75	37.80
	4	13.58	11.70	3.56	8.07	28.00
	5	14.55	13.00	3.19	10.12	40.60
Mean ±STD		14.55±0.69a	11.44±2.78b	3.11±0.49ab	8.30±1.21b	28.56±10.96b
South	1	14.55	25.35	2.62	10.71	15.40
	2	15.52	16.90	3.19	10.42	26.60
	3	13.58	14.95	2.25	17.90	33.60
	4	19.39	11.70	2.62	8.95	35.00
	5	17.46	18.85	2.44	7.92	39.20
Mean ±STD		16.10±2.34a	17.55±5.10a	2.62±0.35bc	11.18±3.92ab	29.96±9.32b
FPL(FAO/WHO)		0.20	1.30	0.10	67.90	425.00

FPL = Food Permissible Limit for Heavy Metals

3.6 Heavy metal content on the tubers of cassava harvested from the soil around Egbu mechanic village

The concentrations of heavy metals in cassava tubers reveal significant accumulation of Cd, Cr, and As across all sampling locations (Table 6). Cadmium ranged from 13.77 to 20.75 mg/kg, far exceeding the FAO/WHO permissible limit

of 0.20 mg/kg, with the highest value observed in the northern direction. This indicates strong soil–plant transfer and highlights Cd as the major contaminant of concern, likely enhanced by the slightly acidic and sandy soil conditions that favor its mobility (Zhang et al., 2023). Chromium concentrations (5.33–12.09 mg/kg) also exceeded the permissible limit of 1.30

mg/kg in all directions, while arsenic levels (1.87–2.92 mg/kg) were consistently above the safe limit of 0.10 mg/kg. The elevated levels of these metals suggest effective uptake and accumulation in cassava tubers, raising concerns about food safety and long-term exposure risks (Alloway, 2013; Ramos-Romero et al., 2026).

In contrast, nickel (6.69–10.83 mg/kg) and iron (6.72–10.08 mg/kg) remained within their respective permissible limits,

indicating lower immediate risk. However, their consistent presence reflects ongoing uptake from contaminated soils (Nie & Huang, 2024). The results demonstrate that cassava tubers cultivated around the study area are contaminated with toxic metals, particularly Cd, Cr, and As, posing potential health risks through dietary intake. This underscores the impact of mechanic village activities and the need for continuous monitoring and soil management interventions (Neina, 2019).

Table 6: Heavy metal content on the tubers of cassava harvested from the soils around Egbu mechanic village

Directions	Sampling points	Cd	Cr	As	Ni	Fe
		mg/kg				
Control	1	14.55	12.35	1.69	8.51	5.60
	2	12.61	12.35	2.25	4.70	15.40
	3	14.55	11.05	1.50	7.19	8.40
	4	14.55	12.35	1.69	8.51	5.60
	5	12.61	12.35	2.25	4.70	15.40
Mean ±STD		13.77±1.06b	12.09±0.58a	1.87±0.35b	6.72±1.93b	10.08±4.99a
East	1	10.67	9.75	2.06	11.74	5.60
	2	10.67	14.95	2.44	9.98	8.40
	3	12.61	12.35	1.69	9.83	11.20
	4	10.67	9.75	2.06	11.74	5.60
	5	29.09	9.10	2.06	10.86	9.80
Mean ±STD		14.74±8.07b	11.18±2.45ab	2.06±0.27b	10.83±0.92a	8.12±2.50a
North	1	15.52	9.10	3.75	6.46	8.40
	2	25.21	7.80	3.19	8.95	9.80
	3	20.36	11.05	2.62	6.60	9.80
	4	25.21	11.05	2.44	10.86	9.80
	5	17.46	3.90	2.62	4.99	9.80
Mean ±STD		20.75±4.42a	8.58±2.96b	2.92±0.54a	7.57±2.32ab	9.52±0.63a
West	1	18.42	5.20	2.06	7.92	11.20
	2	17.46	5.20	1.69	7.78	5.60
	3	19.39	3.90	2.25	8.07	9.80
	4	18.42	7.80	2.06	11.45	5.60
	5	20.36	4.55	1.31	3.23	7.00
Mean ±STD		18.81±1.11ab	5.33±1.48c	1.87±0.37b	7.69±2.92ab	7.84±2.54a
South	1	17.46	3.25	2.62	2.64	7.00
	2	18.42	5.20	2.25	3.82	7.00
	3	18.42	7.80	1.31	11.00	5.60
	4	17.46	3.25	2.06	12.03	8.40
	5	18.42	7.15	3.00	3.96	5.60
Mean ±STD		18.04±0.53ab	5.33±2.13c	2.25±0.64b	6.69±4.45b	6.72±1.17a
FPL(FAO/WHO)		0.20	1.30	0.10	67.90	425.00

FPL = Food Permissible Limit for Heavy Metals

3.7 Contamination Factor and Degree of Contamination of the soils around Egbu mechanic village

The contamination factor (CF) values indicate varying degrees of heavy metal pollution across soils, cassava peels, and tubers (Table 7). Cadmium (Cd) showed extremely high CF values in all sample types, ranging from 37.06–75.85 in soils, 72.73–120.24 in peels, and 68.85–103.76 in tubers, indicating very high contamination. The overall degree of contamination further confirms Cd as the dominant pollutant, reflecting strong anthropogenic inputs and high mobility under acidic soil conditions (Zhang et al., 2023). Chromium (Cr) exhibited low CF values in soils (0.01–0.07), suggesting no contamination; however, higher values in peels (4.70–13.50) and tubers (4.10–9.30) indicate considerable to very high accumulation in plant tissues. This suggests efficient uptake and

bioaccumulation by cassava despite low soil concentrations (Alloway, 2013).

Arsenic (As) followed a similar pattern, with low soil CF (0.23–0.31) but very high values in peels (19.86–34.85) and tubers (18.73–29.23), indicating significant bioavailability and plant uptake. This highlights potential long-term health risks due to its persistence and toxicity (Ramos-Romero et al., 2026). In contrast, nickel (Ni) and iron (Fe) showed low CF values across all sample types, indicating minimal contamination. Their overall contamination degrees were negligible, suggesting limited environmental risk (Nie & Huang, 2024). In general, the results reveal that Cd is the primary contaminant in the study area, while As and Cr show significant bioaccumulation in cassava. The high CF values in plant tissues compared to soils emphasize the role of soil properties and plant uptake mechanisms in metal transfer, underscoring potential food safety concerns (Neina, 2019).

Table 7: Contamination Factor and Degree of Contamination of the soils around Egbu mechanic village

Directions	CF _{Cd}			CF _{Cr}			CF _{As}			CF _{Ni}			CF _{Fe}		
	Soil	Peel	Tuber	Soil	Peel	Tuber	Soil	Peel	Tuber	Soil	Peel	Tuber	Soil	Peel	Tuber
Control	56.89	114.42	68.85	0.07	9.00	9.30	0.26	19.86	18.73	0.07	0.19	0.10	0.60	0.05	0.02
East	75.85	97.94	73.70	0.04	4.70	8.60	0.23	30.73	20.61	0.06	0.17	0.16	0.53	0.10	0.02
North	61.20	120.24	103.76	0.02	7.70	6.60	0.29	34.85	29.23	0.04	0.15	0.11	0.71	0.05	0.02
West	37.06	72.73	94.06	0.01	8.80	4.10	0.31	31.10	18.73	0.06	0.12	0.11	0.69	0.07	0.02
South	54.30	80.49	90.18	0.04	13.50	4.10	0.25	26.23	22.48	0.05	0.16	0.10	0.64	0.07	0.02
C _d	285.30	485.82	430.55	0.18	43.70	32.70	1.35	142.77	109.79	0.29	0.80	0.58	3.18	0.34	0.10

3.8 Pollution Load Index (PLI) of cassava peel and cassava tuber of the soils around Egbu mechanic village

The Pollution Load Index (PLI) values (Figure 2) provide an integrated assessment of heavy metal contamination and its transfer from soil to cassava tissues. Soil PLI values across all sampling directions were below unity ($\approx 0.35\text{--}0.55$), indicating moderate contamination without severe cumulative pollution. This suggests that although individual metals such as cadmium and arsenic were elevated, their combined effect in soils remains relatively controlled (Hakanson, 1980; Alloway, 2013). In contrast, cassava tubers recorded PLI values greater than 1 ($\approx 1.7\text{--}2.2$), indicating significant accumulation of heavy metals in the edible portion of the crop. The highest values observed in the northern and eastern directions correspond to areas with greater anthropogenic influence, confirming effective soil-plant transfer of

contaminants. Similar trends of elevated metal uptake in cassava grown in contaminated environments have been reported in Nigeria (Ndukwe et al., 2020).

Cassava peels exhibited the highest PLI values ($\approx 2.7\text{--}3.1$), indicating that they act as major sinks for heavy metals. This pattern reflects preferential accumulation in outer tissues, a phenomenon widely reported for root crops where peels concentrate metals more than internal tissues (Alloway, 2013; McLaughlin et al., 1999). Overall, the consistent trend of Soil < Tuber < Peel demonstrates progressive accumulation along the soil-plant pathway. The PLI values (>1) for both tubers and peels indicate potential food safety risks, particularly from toxic metals such as cadmium and arsenic. These findings highlight the need for continuous monitoring and remediation of contaminated soils to reduce metal transfer into food crops (Tomlinson et al., 1980).

Figure 2: Pollution Load Index (PLI) of cassava peel and cassava tuber of the soils around Egbu

3.9 Bioaccumulations Factor of cassava peel on cassava harvested from soil around Egbu mechanic village

Figure 3 shows that the bioaccumulation factor (BAF) of heavy metals in cassava peel was generally greater than 1 across all sampling locations, indicating active uptake and accumulation from soil (Kabata-Pendias, 2011; Alloway, 2013). The overall accumulation trend followed the order: Fe > Cr > Cd > Ni > As, suggesting that iron was most readily accumulated, while arsenic showed the lowest uptake. The consistently high BAF values confirm that cassava peel functions as a major sink for heavy metals, in line with reports that outer plant tissues preferentially accumulate contaminants (McLaughlin et al., 1999).

Iron exhibited the highest BAF (≈ 7.8 – 17.5), likely reflecting increased availability under prevailing soil conditions. Chromium also showed considerable accumulation (≈ 2.5 –

14.5), possibly enhanced by slightly acidic soil pH, while cadmium (≈ 3.0 – 6.0) demonstrated high mobility and strong plant uptake, consistent with its anthropogenic origin and toxicity (Alloway, 2013; Järup, 2003). Nickel showed moderate accumulation (≈ 3.0 – 6.5), whereas arsenic, though lowest (≈ 1.5 – 2.8), still exceeded unity, indicating active transfer to plant tissues.

Spatial variations revealed higher Fe accumulation in the east, Cr in the west, and Ni in the north, reflecting localized contamination patterns linked to mechanic workshop activities. Overall, the elevated BAF values suggest that cassava peel can serve as a bioindicator of soil contamination, but also poses potential risks if used for food or feed, particularly due to cadmium and arsenic exposure (Smith et al., 2002).

Figure 3: Bioaccumulations Factor of cassava peel on cassava harvested from soil around Egbu mechanic village

3.10 Bioaccumulations Factor of cassava tuber on cassava harvested from soil around Egbu mechanic village

Figure 4 indicates that the bioaccumulation factor (BAF) of heavy metals in cassava tubers was generally greater than 1, confirming active transfer of metals from soil to the edible portion of the plant (Kabata-Pendias, 2011; Alloway, 2013). However, BAF values in tubers were consistently lower than those observed in the peel, indicating reduced but still significant accumulation. The overall trend of metal accumulation followed: Fe > Cr > Cd > Ni > As, similar to the pattern observed in cassava peel. Iron showed the highest accumulation, reflecting its greater availability and plant uptake, while chromium and cadmium also exhibited notable accumulation despite relatively lower soil concentrations. Cadmium's presence in tubers highlights its high

mobility and potential health risk, even at low soil levels (Järup, 2003).

Nickel displayed moderate accumulation, whereas arsenic recorded the lowest BAF values but still exceeded unity, indicating continued transfer into edible tissues. Spatial variations were evident, with higher accumulation of certain metals observed in the northern and eastern locations, likely due to localized contamination from mechanic activities. Despite lower accumulation compared to peel, the fact that tuber BAF values exceeded 1 suggests that cassava tubers are not entirely protected from heavy metal uptake. This raises important food safety concerns, as continuous consumption may lead to bioaccumulation in humans, particularly for toxic metals such as cadmium and arsenic (Alloway, 2013; Smith et al., 2002).

Figure 4: Bioaccumulations Factor of cassava tuber on cassava harvested from soil around Egbu mechanic village

3.11 Biotranslocation Factor of cassava tuber harvested from soil around Egbu mechanic village

The spatial variation of biotranslocation factors (BTFs) across the study locations reveals important patterns in heavy metal mobility and soil–cassava transfer dynamics (Figure 5). Most metals recorded BTF values below the critical threshold of 1, indicating limited transfer from soil to cassava. However, chromium (Cr) in the East and arsenic (As) in the Control slightly exceeded this threshold, suggesting localized enhancement of phytoavailability, likely influenced by site-specific soil conditions and anthropogenic inputs (Alloway, 2013; Mkhonza et al., 2026).

Iron (Fe) exhibited relatively high BTF values in the West and South, indicating greater mobility, possibly due to redox-driven processes affecting iron oxides (Smedley & Kinniburgh, 2002). Nickel (Ni) also showed

moderate transfer, particularly in the West, reflecting its relatively higher mobility and weaker soil binding. In contrast, cadmium (Cd) and arsenic (As) generally displayed lower BTF values across most locations, suggesting restricted translocation, although their presence remains a concern due to potential toxicity even at low levels (Zhang et al., 2020).

Spatially, the West and East locations exhibited higher transfer potentials, indicating heterogeneous contamination patterns likely driven by proximity to mechanic village activities. Although most BTF values were below unity, the proximity of several metals to the threshold highlights the potential for increased uptake under changing environmental conditions. These findings underscore the need for integrated assessment of metal transfer and associated health risks in contaminated agroecosystems (Tiabou et al., 2024; Mkhonza et al., 2026).

Figure 5: Biotranslocation Factor of cassava tuber harvested from soil around Egbu mechanic village

4.0 Conclusion

Mechanic village activities in Egbu significantly alter soil metal dynamics and promote toxic element accumulation in cassava. Sandy, moderately acidic soils enhance Cd mobility and bioavailability, resulting in severe contamination across the soil–plant continuum. Although soil Cr and As levels were low to moderate, their elevated concentrations in cassava indicate strong phytoaccumulation and food-chain transfer. Pollution indices confirm moderate soil contamination but high biological contamination, particularly in edible tissues. Cassava cultivated in proximity to mechanic workshops therefore represents a potential public health risk due to dietary exposure to Cd, Cr, and As. Routine monitoring of heavy metals in soils and food crops in mechanic village environments should be implemented, alongside restrictions on the cultivation of edible root crops in contaminated zones and the promotion of farmer awareness on contamination risks and safe land-use practices. In addition, soil remediation strategies such as biochar application, organic amendments, and liming should be adopted, environmental regulations for proper disposal of mechanic workshop wastes should be enforced, and

human health risk assessments (EDI, THQ, CR) should be conducted to quantify dietary exposure risks.

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